

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B139
 Date: 17 Nov 2005
 Take Off: 10:38:35
 Landing: 15:42:19
 Flight Time: 5h03m44

Campaign: PRE DABEX
Operating Area: Irish Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	CCM mentor	Sue Angold	Directflight
5	Mission Scientist	Jon Taylor	Met Office
6	Flight Manager UT	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	AVAPS (Dropsondes)	Steve Devereau	FAAM
9	AVAPS (Dropsondes) UT	Doug Anderson	FAAM
10	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
11	MARSS/DEIMOS	Ian Rule	Met Office
12	Wet Neph	Simon Osborne	Met Office
13	Mission Scientist UT	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
14	CPI	Ian Crawford	University of Manchester
15	SWS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
16	Mission scientist UT	Stuart Newman	Met Office
17	SWS UT	Claire Mc Connell	Reading University
18	Observer	Terri Kelly	Directflight

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B139
 Date: 17 Nov 2005
 Project: PRE DABEX
 Location: Irish sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
103835		T/O			
104739		videos	10.0 kft	246	start recording
112744	120156	Profile 1	50 ft - 25.0 kft	152	
112950		BBR	1.1 kft	164	extended at descent
113326		change climb rate	3.4 kft	166	1000ft/min @ 3000ft
113536	113820	Interrupt Profile 1	6.0 kft	325	6000ft
114609	114813	Interrupt Profile 1	14.0 kft	145	FL140
115334		cameras	19.3 kft	146	UFC changed
115422	115634	Interrupt Profile 1	20.0 kft	318	FL200
120307	120332	Run 1.1	25.0 kft	353	Run aborted
120347	120848	Run 1.2	25.0 kft	004	BBR retract
121158	121701	Run 1.3	25.0 kft	184	
121916	122418	Run 1.4	25.0 kft	007	
122650	123150	Run 1.5	25.0 kft	188	
123419	123920	Run 1.6	25.0 kft	009	
124050	124551	Run 1.7	25.0 kft	279	
124836	125337	Run 1.8	25.0 kft	103	
130014	130402	Run 1.9	25.0 kft	197	
130654	131359	Run 1.10	25.0 kft	334	
131616	132121	Run 1.11	25.0 kft	068	
132413	133018	Run 1.12	25.0 kft	245	
132853		dropsonde	25.0 kft	245	sonde 1 released
133756	134259	Run 1.13	25.0 kft	151	
134337	134502	Orbit 1	25.0 kft	065	
134635	134804	Orbit 2	25.0 kft	031	
134939	135057	Orbit 3	25.0 - 24.9 kft	332	
135256	135412	Orbit 4	25.0 - 24.4 kft	271	
135625	142918	Profile 2	25.0 - 50 ft	306	bbrs extend
140657	140853	Interrupt Profile 2		125	FL170
141823	141956	Interrupt Profile 2		302	7000ft
142918	143519	Profile 3	50ft - 4.0 kft	306	
143131	143314	Interrupt Profile 3		095	1500ft
143802	144306	Run 2.1	4.0 kft	216	bbr retracted
144652	145152	Run 2.2	3.9 kft	039	
145342	145842	Run 2.3	3.9 kft	220	
150051	150552	Run 2.4	3.9 kft	044	
154219		Land			
154926		Cranfield end position			52'04.36N 0'37.48W

B139 Track 17-NOV-05

FAAM Sortie Brief

Pre-DABEX clear skies test flying

Flight No: B139

Date: 17 Nov 2005

Trial objectives:

To test radiometers and aerosol sampling equipment that are essential to the DABEX campaign (Jan-Feb '06). These instruments include: (1) wet neph, (2) BBRs, (3) SHIMS, (4) SWS, (5) IR camera, (5) CVI and (6) PCASP.

Location:

Suitable sea area: Irish Sea or ~~South West Approaches~~.

Weather:

Clear sky column preferred, else homogenous stratocumulus; advection of pollution over the sea is useful for wet-neph testing.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield. [1030Z]
2. [1030] Transit out to operating area over sea, to arrive at minimum permitted altitude (50 ft) [40 mins]
3. [1110] Profile ascent to FL250, at rate 500 ft/min below 3000 ft increasing to 1000 ft/min above [30 mins]
4. [1140] Four reciprocal 5 min runs, over land, legs orientated into- and down- Sun. [30 mins]
5. [1210] ... followed by L-pattern at FL250, 5 min legs, legs orientated into-, down- and 2×across- Sun. [30 mins]
6. [1240] Second L-pattern at FL250, 5 min legs, legs orientated at 45 degrees to the first L-pattern. During pattern release one sonde (training). [30 mins]
7. [1310] Series of four orbits at FL250, bank angle to be maximum (60deg) [10 mins]
8. [1320] Profile descent to 2000 ft (or level to be determined by mission scientist), over sea, at rate of 1000 ft/min above 5000 ft, 500ft/min below this [25 mins]
9. [1345] Four reciprocal 5 min SLRs over sea, orientated into- and down-Sun [30 mins]
10. [1415] Profile descent to 50 ft at rate of 500ft/min [25 mins]
11. [1420] Two reciprocal 5 min SLRs over sea at 100 ft, orientated into- and down-Sun [15 mins]
12. [1435] Profile ascent from 50 ft to 600 ft (500 ft/min) followed by series of four orbits, bank angle to be 60deg [15 mins]
13. [1450] Transit back to base [40 mins]
14. [1530] Land.

Mission scientist's debrief
Flight B139, 17 November 2005

Sortie aims:

Pre-DABEX tests of SWS, BBRs and wet nephelometer. The area north and west of Wales was identified as likely clear of cloud based on forecasts, and therefore suitable for SWS views over a range of solar scattering angles in clear skies.

Summary

Transit to the operating area was at FL100, followed by descent to 50 feet over Cardigan Bay and a profile ascent to FL250. PCASP aerosol counts were relatively low during the profile, 10-100/cc. A series of reciprocal runs into- and down-sun were performed at FL250, followed by L-patterns (i) into-, down- and across-sun, and (ii) at 45 degrees to (i), as SWS and BBR tests. Although some 2D-C signal was picked up times, indicating the presence cloud particles at low concentrations, the majority of the runs were conducted in clear air. One sonde was dropped as a training exercise (not expected to provide accurate data). Towards the end of this segment indications of liquid water at -38°C were found, as well as 50-100 micron sized ice particles. A series of orbits followed, two at around 50° then 55° and 60° (this last however caused a loss of altitude during orbit of 600 feet). The aircraft intermittently contrailed (see mission scientist's log for engine settings).

A profile down to the surface over the sea followed, to 50 feet, monitoring the aerosol concentration which peaked at approximately 250/cc at 4500 feet. Levelling during ascent at 4000 feet to conduct in- and down-sun runs PCASP concentrations of 150-300 were encountered, giving something for the wet nephelometer to sample. The low sun (~80 degrees solar zenith angle) during these runs meant that these SWS data are probably affected by clouds obscuring the sun for much of the time.

Instrument faults

Initial problems with wet nephelometer cleared during sortie.

SWS near-infrared module was unavailable at first, but recovered in time for science runs.

Total water probe was inoperable during the flight.

FWVS did not work very well.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: STUART NEWMAN

Flight No **B.139**.....
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Date **17/11/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
102825	0				TAKE OFF
103835		FL100			Transit at FL100
1055					Clear skies in Birmingham area Problems with SWS lw channel and wet-nephelometer in transit - Total Water U/S
1105					Approaching Welsh borders region, Some Ci, few isol. Cu below
1115					SWS channel is back
1120					Over Cardigan Bay, largely clear
1124					Aerosol incr. from 60 to 180 locally ^{below} descending into Bay area Very calm sea state
112744	PI	50ft ↑	310	52.0 N 1.8 W	500 ft/min
1130			164	52.5 4.0 W	Wet-neph reporting < 3000 ft - 100, pretty clean
1133		3000'	166	52.3 4.0 W	Increasing rate of climb to 1000'/min
1135		5700'			10 ↑ 100 aerosol count PCASP
113536	Intermittent PI	FL060			
113730			321	52.2 4.1 W	
113820	Recommence PI	FL060 ↑	326	52.3 4.2 W	
114330		FL112	322	52.5 N 4.5 W	Few wisps of high Ci to west, looks clear overhead
1145		FL128		52.6 4.6	Some low level cloud (Sc) here
114609	Intermittent PI	FL140		52.6 N 4.7 W	Just passed through moist layer on TP
114813	Rec. PI	FL140 ↑			Recommence profile, finding area largely clear of clouds
115422	Intermittent PI	FL200		52.1 4.2	above and below
115634	Rec. PI	FL200 ↑	319	52.2 N 4.1 W	

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.139**
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 Date **17/11/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					No contrails 90.2 NI 74 TGT 89 N2 6.7 FF/FU
					solar azim 179
120347	RI.2		005		Sunny reciprocal run Started down sun
1207					Contrailing 81.8 last 2 runs 60.4 84.3 4.4
120830					Few patches cloud above and none at flight level
120848	end RI.2				Into cloud at end of run 2D-C picking up signal S. azim 182 for next run
121158	RI.3				Into-sun run Few wisps Ci, but largely clear above.
121701	end 1.3				
121916	1.4	F2250	006		Down sun Saz. 184 approaching cloud at end of run
122418	end 1.4	"			End of run some 2D-C signal (AKIS zenith run) - some windows temp variation for AKIS
122650	1.5	F2250	187		Into-sun
123150	end 1.5	"			
123419	1.6				Start of L-pattern Contrailing 81.8 (look high 62.4 humidity 84.2 from pressure 4.5 of cloud at own altitude)
123920	end				some 2D signal at end of run
124050	1.7	F2250	278	52.4 4.0w	across-sun leg
1242					Picked up some ice on 2C sws 6deg off zenith
124540	end 1.7				

RI.1 aborted

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B. 139**
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
124836	R1.8	FL250	103	52.4N 4.3W	Cross-sun run, looks clear above and below
1252					Bit of ice around, some cloud at aircraft altitude (wispy)
125337	end R1.8				Over land at end of run
					Tacking to avoid airways
1259					S. azim 194 some wispy cloud at coast
130014	R1.9	FL250	197	52.3N 3.8W	Over land this run Sc cloud bank below to W.
130402	end R1.9				
130654	R1.10	FL250	334	52.1 4.1	Start of L-pattern at 45° to first Bit of cloud at start of run
					Extension of run (into curve) by ~2 km S. azim 197
131359	end R1.10				Classic Ci out to E Over Bay for latter part of run
1315					Turning, in cloud
131616	R1.11	FL250	066	52.6 4.1	S. azim 198 Forced to operate over land (cannot drop sonde in Aberparth range today)
					Some scattered Ci below, clear above
132121	end R1.11	FL250		52.8N 3.6W	
132413	R1.12	FL250	244	52.7 3.7W	
132830					In some cloud Just over sea, can drop sonde
132853	sonde released				
133018	end R1.12				Wind 75 knots, quite strong
1334					In quite thick cloud 50-100 um ice
					Some indications of liquid water from other probes at -38°C !!
133756	R1.13	FL250	152	52.7 4.1W	S. azim. 203 s. zen 74.8
1340					Some wispy cloud at FL250 and above
134259	end R1.13				
134337					Orbit ~ 50° in wispy cloud for some of orbit

134502

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.139**.....

 Date **17/11/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134635	02				Second orbit, ARIES has 50° is max. achievable crashed
4804	end				
4939	03				Third orbit 55° ARIES back up at end of orbit
5057	end				
5256	04	FL250			Four orbit, near 60°
5412	end	FL243			Lost 600 ft in orbit
	P2	FL250		52.3 3.9	
135800					In cloud last minute or so
141823	interr. P2	7000ft	127	52.3 3.8	Profile down interrupted at 7000ft
141956	recomm. P2		303	52.2 3.9	leak in PCASP at 5800'
					140/cc relatively stable
					4600' 250/cc
					3500' 200/cc
					3100' 150/cc
					2600' 100/cc
					1900' 10-15/cc
1426	(P2)	1400			1290' 75-100 some wispy Ci above, not much
					560' 100-150/cc
142918	end P2				310' 80/cc
142918	Start P3				Decided to profile up to 3500' to get in aerosol layer
143131	interr. P3	1500'			Bardsey Island almost underneath
143314	Recomm. P3				Cloud encroaching above end of profile readings 90
					Adjusted to 4000 feet,
					Some 100+ values so going with that for St L

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: Operator: DRS time: DAU1 time: DAU2 time: DAU3 time: AUX1 time: AUX2 time: Page 1 of 1

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
112744	100	0.06	1	10												Start p1	
113133	50	0.06	1	10												020	
1134	10	0.06	1													040	
113536	60	0.07	1													060	
114030	10	0.06	1													080	
114245	10	0.07	1													100	
114611	15	0.06	1													140	
115415	10	0.06	1													200	
115831	10	0.06	1													220	
1202	50	0.06														250	
120347	25	0.06														Start run 1.1	
1207	10	0.06														1207	
120848																End run 1.2	
121158	10	0.06	2													Start run 1.3	
1214	15	0.06	2														
121701	15	0.06														End run 1.3	
121916	15	0.06														Start run 1.4	
1221	15	0.06															
122418	20	0.06														End run 1.4	
122650	15	0.06														Start run 1.5	
1229	10	0.06															
1231	20	0.06															
123150																End 1.5	
																Start run 1.6	

a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B139 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	103000 155000 10 PMSDATA:	2D-C only processed FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B139_2Dx_IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	24/11/05	Complete, file on O:\CloudPhysics Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: B139 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B139_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unkown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B139_PROC2D	1 103000 155000 0.2 8 2 24/11/05	2D-C only processed Note the particle type complete
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B139_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B139_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	24/11/05	
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B139_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B139_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	24/11/05	complete

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 139	Date	17/Nov/05	Operator(s)	S. Rogers	log page	1 of 5
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

0823	POWER UP					
082540	-	-	0°	500	1000	Cal + Scene Clear sky. Some C. T: 17°C
0827	Power off					
1041	TAKE OFF					Power up.
1052	Climb		0°	400	1000	No NIR signal.
1101	Transit		0°	400	1000	Cal + scene Shutter stuck?
1112	"		0°	400	1000	Cal. Reset shutter ok.
1113	Restart.					NIR is back
1115			0°	400	1000	Cal + scene T: 11°C
112744	P1	50' ↑	"	"	"	Some VIS clipping during turn.
113500		5700'	"	"	"	Some VIS clipping
1150			"	"	"	Cal + scene
115350		FL200	0°	400	1000	Cal
120309		250' FL200	40° F	400	1000	40 F
120433			40 A			40 A
120501			0			0
120532			20 F			20 F
120506			60 A			60 A
120532			30 A			30 A
120603			30 F			30 F cloud?
120632			10 A			10 A
120802			50 A			50 A cloud?
120834			10 F			10 F Some VIS clip.
120857				400	1000	20 A
121200			40 F			Cal. in turn.
121237			40 A			40 F
121305			0			40 A
121331			20 F			0
121407			60 A			20 F
121435			30 A			60 A
121501			30 F			30 A Some VIS clipping.
121534			10 A			30 F
121603			50 A			10 A
121641			10 F			50 A
			20 A			10 F T: 15°C
						20 A

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B131** Date **17/Nov/05** Operator(s) **S. Roberts** log page **2** of **5**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

12 12 19		FL250	40 F	400	1000	40 F
12 20			25 A			25 A Staff sup.
21 05			0			0
21 35			20 F			20 F
21 08			60 A			60 A
21 35			30 A			30 A
23 03			30 F			30 F
12 23 33			10 A			10 A
24 04			50 A			50 A VIS clipping
12 26 52				350	1000	Cal x2 (shutter?)
			40 F			40 F
12 27 39			40 A			40 A
12 28 14			0			0
12 28 45			20 F			20 F
29 23			60 A			60 A
29 50			30 A			30 A
12 30 18			30 F			30 F
12 30 47			10 A			10 A
31 16			50 A			50 A
12 31 50			10 F			10 F + end of Run.
12 32 40				350	1000	Cal
12 34 22			40 F	350	1000	40 F
12 35 28			40 A			40 A Some VIS clipping Till-c
12 36 07			0			0
12 36 35			20 F			20 F
			60 A			60 A
12 38 10			30 A			30 A
12 38 42			30 F			30 F
12 39 12			10 A			10 A
12 39 40						Cal
12 40 50	R1.7	FL250	6 F	350	1000	Across sun.
12 46 00			"	"	"	Cal
12 46 20			"	"	"	Scene
12 53 37						Cal

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 129	Date	17/Nov/03	Operator(s)		log page	3	of	5
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

13 00 15	R1-9	FL250	40F	400	1000	40F			
13 00 55			40A			40A			
13 01 25			0			0			
13 01 57			20F			20F			
13 02 45			60A			60A			
13 03 20			30A			30A			
13 03 57			30F			30F			
13 04 17				400	1000	Cal			T:15
13 06 55		FL250	6F	400	1000	450	between in (up-down and across)		
13 14 09		FL250	6F	400	1000	Cal			
13 14 57	R1-11	"	"	350	"	Scene	VIS clipping during maneuver		
13 21				350	1000	Cal			
13 22 50	R1-12	"	6F	350	1000	Scene	Some thin cloud above?		
13 30 20		"	6F	350	1000	Cal			
13 30 45		"	6F	350	1000	Scene	Some cloud above?		T:16
13 37 58	R1-13	"	"	"	"				
13 43 08		FL250	6F	300	1000	Cal			left
13 43 32	Orbit 11		"	"	"	Scene	VIS clipping		50° bank
13 45 10			"	250	"	Cal			
13 45 32			"	"	"	Scene			right T:17
13 46 37	02								
13 49 38	03					Scene	Some VIS clip.		55° left bank
13 52 58	04					Cl, VIS at start of orbit			
13 55 32	-	FL250	6F	250	1000	Cal			rev.
13 56 26		FL250 ↓	6F	300	1000	Cal			
13 56 55		P2 ↓	"	"	"	Scene.			
14 29 24		50 ft	6F	300	1000	Cal			T:16
14 30 00		↑	"	"	"	Scene.	14 33 55 N/A N/A		T:13
14 35 05		FL035	"	300	1000	Cal + scene	Some cloud.		
14 38 12			40F			40F			
14 38 44			40A			40A			
14 38 17			0			0			
14 39 50			20F			20F			
14 40 16			60A			60A			
14 40 50			30F			30F			
14 41 18			10A			10A			
14 41 47			50A			50A			
14 42 16			10F			10F			
14 42 46			20A			20A			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 139	Date	17/NOV/05	Operator(s)	S. RODERS	log page	8 of 5
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

14 42 15		FL040 FL035	20A	300	1000	Cal.	T: 11°C
14 46 33		"	40F	"	"	40F	Rt. 144252
4649			40A			40A	
14 48 00			0			0	
14 48 31			20F			20F	
14 48 59			60A			60A	
14 49 32			30A			30A	
14 50 04			30F			30F	
14 51 31			10A			10A	
14 51 58			50A			50A	
14 52 29		"	10F	"	"	10F	
			20A			20A	
14 52 06		FL040	-	300	1000	Cal.	
14 52 50		"	-	250	1000	Cal.	
14 53 40		FL040	40F	250	1000	40F	
14 54 32			40A			40A	
14 54 59			0			0	
14 55 30			20F			20F	
14 55 59			60A			60A	
14 56 30			30A			30A	
14 57 02			30F			30F	
14 57 30			10A			10A	
14 58 00			50A			50A	
14 58 30			10F	250	1000	10F	
						20A	
14 58 47				250	1000	Cal.	
15 00 54		FL040	40F	250	1000	40F	
15 01 30			40A	"	"	40A	
15 02 00			0	"	"	0	
15 02 33			20F	"	"	20F	
15 03 01			60A	"	"	60A	
15 03 31			30A	"	"	30A	
15 04 01			30F	"	"	30F	
15 04 30			10A	"	"	10A	
15 05 01			50A	"	"	50A	
15 05 31			10F	"	"	10F	
0558			20A			20A	
15 05 58		FL040	-	250	1000	Cal.	
							T: 15°C

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	17/11/05	Flight	B139	log pages
Operator(s)	Ian Rule	Campaign	Pre-Dabex			
Departure	Cranfield	Arrival	Cranfield			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers	
FERA on	at time 0822 ish
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16 °C Ch 17 °C Ch18 °C
Temperature controller set points	54°C 58°C -20 40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time 0822 ish
Initial target temperatures	Hot Cold
Target heating	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time 0822 ish
Scan indication	Monitor Visual

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	
Turn on Deimos CPU	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***	
Start Deimos Software	at time 0824 ish
Initial target temperatures	Hot Cold
Target heating	
Scan indication	Monitor Visual
Weather	Cloud 2/8 Ci Precip nil Surface Dry Pressure 996 Other Clear and cold IAT = 7.2

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} + 0.0$ at time 0922
Brightness temps 'sensible'	MARSS good except ch16 u/s, Deimos sensible but noisy
Target temps	MARSS: Hot 344 Cold 278 Deimos: Hot 342 Cold 287
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-) 55 Ch3 A (-) 39 Ch1 B (-) 55 Ch3 B (-) 39 Ch16 (40-44) 0 Ch17 (45-49) 34 Ch18 (40-44) 37 Ch19 (40-44) 37 Ch20 (44-48) 40

Power changeover

Headset on before start	
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)	
Exit Deimos Software (x)	
POWER CHANGEOVER	
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton
Restart Deimos Software	
System running again	at time

Flight #	B	Date	Operator(s)	log page	2	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks	Sys			
0919			Stop logging to set laptop time = DRS +/- 0				
0922			Restart logging				
1005			Stop MARSS and Deimos to reset PC times				
1007			Start recording, boths PC's equal to DRS time				
1025			Deimos stopped for power change, strange effect on MARSS data around power change, poss heat from engines?				
103837			T/o Cranfield				
1045			MARSS good apart from ch 16, Deimos good but noisy				
1119			Instruments correctly registered coasting out, and back in...				
112744	P1	50'	Start profile, interesting peak in MARSS and Deimos data at start of profile, or just before. Poss angle change at bottom of descent?				
1132			Laptop time check, = DRS + 2 s				
1154			Over land				
120157	P1	FL250	End profile				
120349	R1.2	FL250	Start run, down sun				
120850	R1.2		End run				
121200	R1.3	FL250	Start run, into sun				
121701	R1.3		End run				
121916	R1.4	FL250	Start run, down sun, marssmon crashed about 1224				
122418			End run				
122650	R1.5	FL250	Start run, into sun				
123150			End run				
123419	R1.6	FL250	Start run, down sun, L pattern				
123922			End run				
124051	R1.7	FL250	Start run, across sun, sun on port side, L pattern				
1242			Laptop time check, = DRS + approx 3.5 s				
124552		FL250	End run				
124838	R1.8	FL250	Start run, across sun, sun on starboard side, L pattern				
125339			End run				
130015	R1.9	FL250	Start run, up sun, L pattern				
130404			End run				
130655	R1.10	FL250	Start run, second L pattern				
131359			End run				
131616	R1.11	FL250	Start run, second L pattern				
132121			End run				
132415	R1.12	FL250	Start run, second L pattern, sonde dropped				
133018			End run				
133755	R1.13	FL250	Start run, second L pattern				
134300			End run				
134337	O1	FL250	Start orbit, 50 deg, 045 heading, LHD				
134502			End orbit				
134635	O2	FL250	Start orbit, 50 deg, RHD, 030 heading				
134804			End orbit				
134939	O3	FL250	Start orbit, 55 deg, LHD,				

ARIES flight log

Flight: B139

Location: IRISH SEA

page 1 of 5

Date: 17-11-5

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution:

Gain A: 2 B: 4/2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
062115	preflight	B139B	C	28.2	22.6	11.6	-190.6	15.1	CH2	...just checking (1:47?!) (1:40)
082338	"	B139C	C	27.3	22.6	11.5	-190.6	16.3	CH2	
092928	"	B139D	C	71	31	10.6	-189.9	21.4	N1	1 min spot on!
093100	"	B139E	C	71	31	10.8	-189.9	21.6	CH2	gain B too high (1.51)
093637	"	B139F	O	71.3	30.9	11.6	-189.6	21.9	CH2	gains (2,2)
093900	"	B139G	O	71.5	30.8	11.9	-189.9	22.0	Z1 x 5	gains (2,4)
094410	"	B139H	C	71.2	31.1	11.9	-189.9	22.3	CH2 x 4	gain (2,2)
100356	"	B139I	O	71.3	30.2	13.1	-189.9	23.5	CH1 x 1	"
100527	"	B139J	O	71.3	31.1	13.0	-189.9	23.6	Z1 x 5	gains (2,4)
101132	"	B139K	O	71	31	13.5	-190	24.1	CH2 x 1	" (2,2)
1021			C							Engine start
102420	on pan	B139L	O	71	31	14	-190	24	CH1 x 1	Power transfer during trans. ^{data}
102530	"	B139M	O	71	31	14	-190	25	Z1 x 3	
102834	taxi	B139N	C						CH1 x 1	Thru Ci above →
103837	T/O									
105040	transit	B139O	O							Software restarted
110415	"	B139P	C	71	31	2	-190	22.4	CH2 x 1 (gain 2,2)	std turn 110459
110650?	"	B139Q	O	70	31	2	-190	19.9	Z1 x 5	aborted
110900	"	B139R	O	70	31	1.9	-190	15.6	Z1 x 4	gains 2,4

ARIES flight log

Flight: B139

Location: IRISH SEA

page 2 of 5

Date: 17-11-5

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
11 1353	transit	B139S	C	71	31	2.9	-190	16.4	CH1 x1	gains 2,2
11 1600	"	B139T	O	71	31	2.5	-190	16.7	Z1 x5	gains 2,4 descending Rate!
11 2152	descending	B139U	C	71	31	2.9	-190	14.7	CH1 x1	gains 2,2
1134	PI		C							overfly Aberystwyth ~4500'
-			C	71	31	6.0	-190	2.1	-	1 Comedey Cu E of Aberystwyth
11 5235	PI ↑ R2200 +	B139V	C	71	31	2.6	-190	19.8	CH2 x1	gains (2,2)
120149	PI ↑ R246	B139W	C	71	31	-2.3	-190	19	CH1 x1	slbd turn
120315?	R1.1	B139X	C	71	31	-5	-190	17.4	N1 x5	run aborted & restarted.
										poss some cloud at end? aries run through
120807	R1.2	B139Y	C	71	31	-8	-190	15	CH2 x1	1 min before end of run
										gain 2,4! aborted
121032	turn	B139Z	C	71	31	-9	-190	16.8	CH1	gains 2,2
121202	R1.3	B139 φ	C	71	31	-9	-190	17.5	N1 x5	"
121633	ER1.3	B1391	C	71	31	-12	-190	17	CH1 x1	port turn
121925	R1.4	B1392	O	71	31	-14	-190	18	Z1 x5	gains (2,2)
122455	ER1.4	B1393	C	71	30	-16	-190	10.1	CH1 x1	" port turn in cloud
122654	R1.5	B1394	C	71	31	-17	-190	13.4	N1 x5	gains 2,4
123209	ER1.5	B1395	C						CH1 x1	gains 2,4! aborted
123311	port turn	B1396	C	71	30	-16	-190	17	"	" (we slanted quickly but didn't reset gains - fool! fool!

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452

ARIES flight log

Flight: B139

Location: Cardigan Bay

page 3 of 5

Date: 17-11-5

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2/4

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
123430	R1.6	B1397	C	71	31	-17	-190	18	N1 x 5	gain 2, 4
123736	R1.6	B1398	C	71	31	-17	-190	17	CH1 x 1	" S ← E! abt.
123846	"	B1399	C	71	31	-17	-190	17	CH1 x 1	gain 2, 2
124055	R1.7	C139A	C/O	71	32	-18	-190	16	Z1 x 5	1st 20 sec. Sht. closed. g(2,4)
124635	Stbd turn	C139B	C	71	31	-18	-190	9.5	CH1 x 1	gain(2, 2)
124840	R1.8	C139C	C	71	31	-18	-190	13	N1 over x 5	gain(2, 2)
125340	ER1.8	C139D	C	71	31	-18	-190	15	CH1 x 1	gain(2, 2)
12 130020	R1.9	C139E	C	71	31	-18	-190	18	N1 x 5	" (2, 4)
									over land - aborted.	
120250?	R1.9	C139f	O	70	31	-19	-190	13	Z1 x 2	gain(2, 4)
130402	ER1.9	→ C								run cut short.
130534	Stbd turn	C139G	C	71	30	-18	-190	13	CH1 x 1	gain(2, 2)
130714	R1.10	C139H	C	71	31	-19	-190	14	N1 x 5	some cloud. gain(2, 4)
131148	R1.10	C139I	C	70	31	-18	-190	15	N1 x 2	gain(2, 4)
131351	ER1.10	C139J	C	71	31	-18	-190	15	CH1 x 1	" S ← E
131458	Stbd turn	C139K	C	71	31	-18	-190	17	"	gain 2, 2 in cloud
131638	R1.11	C139L	O	70	31	-18	-190	17	Z1 x 5	gain(2, 2) Over Barmouth
	ARIES CLOCK	LEADING							DRS BY 2 SECS.	
132230	Stbd port turn	C139	C	71	31	-20	-190	8.8	CH1 x 1	gain 2, 2

occ. oblique land.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B139

Location: Condagar Bay

page 4 of 5

Date: 17-11-5

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2/4

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
132422	R1.12	C139N	C	71	31	-19	-190	13	N1x5	gain 2,2 mostly land. misjudged how far to coast.
132903	R1.12	C139O	C	70	31	-19	-190	15	N1x1	in cloud.
133030	Stbd turn	C139P	C	71	31	-19	-190	15	CH1x1	gain 2,2 cloud.
133643	Stbd ~	C139Q	C						N1x5	gain 2,2
133756	R1.13		C	71	30	-18			CH1x1	
134216	ER1.13	C139R	C	71	31	-18	-190		Z1x1	gain 2,4
1343	01	C139S	O	71	31	-19	-190	13		
1346	02	C139T	O	71	31	-19	-190		Z1x1	CRASH.
135216		C139V	C	71	30	-19	-190	18	CH1x1	?
135322	03	C139W	O	71	31	18	-190	17	Z1x1	gain 2,2
135531		C139X	C	71	30	-18	-190	15	CH1x1	"
143802	R2.1.400	C139Y	C	71	31	*6	-190	18	"	gain 2,2
143950	"	C139Z	C	71	31	6	-190	19	N1x3	"
144258	ER2.1	C139	C	71	31	6	-190	17	CH1x1	"
144655	R2.2	C1391	O	60	31	6	-190	15	Z1x4	" HBB dropped to 50 sec
145200	ER2.2	C1392	C	71	31	6	-190	14	CH1x1	Stbd turn.
145346	R2.3	C1393	O	69.3	31	6	-190	16	Z1x4	Temp -2.38 Costrick.
145846	ER2.3	C1394	C	71	31	7	-190	18	CH1x1	gain 2,2

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.139**.....

 Date ...12/11/05.....

 Operator's name: ...S.P. OSBORNE.....

 Page ...1... of ...5...

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
~110000								System boot-up ok. → all comms except chiller. (THREAT)
	10	TIME	CHECK	DRS	TIME	WET Neph	LOG TIME	IS 3 SECONDS BEHIND (GPS TIME)
1105	—	FL100	9.5	23%	66%			TRANSIT - residual moisture in tube?
1108			~20	~10%	DECREASING			Set flow to 4.2L
111800			~10		INCREASING			Lower flow rate → wet neph RH goes up.
1123	descending	3000'		25%	52%			Revised up (PDRSP). Increase in RH ambient. Use dry pressure ≈ 1.5 × 10 ⁻⁵ m ²
112740	P1	50'		40%	56%			Start profile ascent over the sea. growth factor set to 0 due to similar RHs. Revised droplets. Pass more in 100/cc clean!!
114500	P17	3500' FL 127		13%	51%			RH5 (re wet neph) ≈ 21% is this correct ??? Try re-starting wet neph? RH1 ≈ RH2 ≈ RH3 ≈ RH5. → RH wet wrong?
114725								Switched wet neph OFF
114845								" " ON → & recording ok do
114930					40%			possible leakage of H ₂ O in wet neph !!! software without re-boot !!
115740			4.8	39%	45%		sample pump OFF (bat)	

rain?
 air?
 erroneous data?

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B**.....139.....

 Date17/1/25.....

 Operator's name: S. P. OSBORN.....

 Page 2 of 2

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1159 ₁₀					drupples			→ 34% with pump off ↓ → does this imply no water in wet cell? Yes! ⇒ RH5 sensor is dodgy?
120230								empty n/a
120300				10%	22%			empty n/a
120434		R250	10					empty n/a
1208								empty n/a
121000	10km	R250	10	0% (!)	33%			empty n/a
122655	10km	R250	10	0%	33%			empty n/a
123940	10km	R250	10.2	0%	37%			empty n/a

pump on → RH's ~ zero here.
 hitting cloud!! yikes.
 RH1 = 6%, RH3 = 5%, RH5 = 10%
 I think we need to calibrate all the RH sensors formally.
 RH1 = 6%, RH3 = 31%, RH5 = 14.6%
 T_{in} = 21.1°C (→ seems high, could it be correct?)
 T_{outside} ≈ -38°C ∴ } ambient.
 T_{in} ≈ -37.1°C } high RH!!
 RH1 = 5%, RH3 = 30%, RH5 = 51%
 ↑
 strange.

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B**.....*139*.....

 Date *13/11/05*.....

 Operator's name: *S.P. USANKAR*.....

 Page *3* of *5*.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
125012	R250	Pattern	10.2	0%	37.8%			RH1 = 4.8%, RH3 = 3%, RH5 = 8.8%, T _{in} = 21.0°C <u>RH5</u> → drifting up & down of its own accord!!
130410	R250	Pattern	10.1	0%	43.6%			RH1 = 4.8%, RH3 = 3.0%, RH5 = 18.7% T _{in} = 20.3°C
135800								Pin slides with WET
140124			10.3	0%	51%		↑	Go to 30°C
140400							30°C	
140500	R2↓	R170	9.4	0%	73%	↔	30°C	RH3 = 45% → eq? RH5 = 33% eq?
140940	R2↓	R140	10.3	0.8%	86%	↔	30°C	RH1 = 7%, RH3 = 44%, RH5 = 73% (better!)
141340	R2↓	R110	9.0	1.5	88%	↔	30°C	→ H ₂ O level too low, water not circulating Top of the Pin chiller
141600								clean like pin chiller
141800	↓	R070	9.2	5.7%	87.5%	↔	30°C	Dsp v. low but true now. PeASP up a little
142105		600'			91%			PeASP 136/cc. σ _{sp} (0.05 μm) ~ 1.5 x 10 ⁻⁵ m ⁻¹
142250	↓	450'	9.5	14%	25%	↔	30°C	250/cc PeASP RH5 = 88% (seems ok) RH1 = 23%, RH3 = 18%, RH4 = 26% (oleic)
142555	↓	1800'	9.3	16%	93%	↔	30°C	
		1500'		24%	96%	↔	30°C	In MRB? Turbulence - GF is v. variable
142950						↓	down.	SEA T ₄₀₀ = +6°C at base of profile.
143100				30%	93%			Water dripping from wet neph connection <u>Warrgh!!!</u>

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.139**

 Date 17/4/05

 Operator's name: S. L. Osborne

 Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow (lpm)	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
								Water trays not full ... so how did water leak from one wet neph connection ???
143355	R7	2400'	8.9	29%	91.4%	↔	17°C	Water temp lower to keep RH _{wet} high. RH _S = RH _{wet} !! Cakes. Start run RH sensors look v. sensible.
	R2.1	4000'	9.8	22.6%	90.3%	↓	17°C at start	Start run in slight cross RH _S ~ 15%. ↳ drop T _{water} to 6°C at start of this run. RH _S ~ 25%.
14400								RH _S (one wet read) dropping to 70%
144123							8.8°C	RH _{wet} ~ 89% v. slow to drop.
144303		4000'	9.7	22.6%	85%		(5°C)	End run. RH _{wet} ramping down slowly (RH _S = 65%) RH _S ~ 30% at turn.
144652	R2.2	4000'	9.6	24%	81%	↔	5°C	Start run RH _S = 57%. Wet neph must be <u>wet</u> RH _S : 150-200cc.
145000	R7.7	4000'	9.6	23%	78%	↔	5°C	RH _S = 51.4% $\frac{V_{sp}^{wet}}{V_{sp}^{dry}} = \frac{0.4 - 2}{RH}$
145153	R7.2	4000'	9.6	21%	77%	↔	5°C	End run. RH _S = 50.8% wet/dry reads wrong way and is off-scale? RH _S should be > unity.
145342	R7.3	4000'	9.5	19.1%	76%	↔	5°C	Start run in v. light aerosol. RH _S = 49.7% * lowest we can achieve?

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B**.....139.....

Date ..17/11/25.....

Operator's name: ...S. R. OSBORNE.....

Page 5... of 5...

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
								Relative \approx 25% higher than RH5.
145614	12.3	4000'	9.2	20.7%	75%	↗		Set to 20°C - Ramp up Temp.
145730	12.3	4000'	9.5	20%	76%	↔	20°C	RH = 59% creeping up...
145941	12.3	4000'	9.6	21.7%	78%	↔	20°C	End Run.
145930	turn	4000'	9.2	22.3%	74.0%	↗	30°C	← go to...
150040		4000'	9.5	21.7%	80.4%	↗	30°C	← now.
150052	12.4	4000'	9.6	20%	81.5%	↔	30°C	Start run.
150142						↗	38°C	← go to...
150208	12.4	4000'	9.6	20.6%	85.6%	↗	38°C	now.
150311	12.4	4000'	9.8	20.0%	89.1%	↗	43°C	← go to...
150411	12.4	4000'	9.5	19.7%	91.4%		43°C	← now. good change - RH!! 20 → 90%
150508				19.1%	(75%)	↓	+5°C	← go to... minimum temp of water.
								→ red light with 76% density ramp down.
150552	12.4	4000'	9.8	16.8%	96.7%	↓	38°C	End Run (last run) of sodie
150709								Climbing in height now.
150755					94.5%		26°C	↓
					Low flow!!			
151050	TRANSIT HOME	4100'	8.1		93.6%			RHS = 85.2% May be RH too high on last run.
151300								RAIN SYSTEM OF WATER.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 139

Date: 17th November 2005

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		N
Heimann		Y	HVPS		N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		Y
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100		Y
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS		N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC		N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	N	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP		N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer		N
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters		N
“ JO1D	Y	N	AMS		N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS		n			
MARSS		Y			
DEIMOS		Y	<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES		Y	NIR TDLAS		N
SWS		Y	2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		N
SO2		N	Formaldehyde		N
NOX		Y	ADA		N
CO		N	CPI		N
ORAC		N	NOxy		N
PAN		N	PTRMS		N
PERCA		N	Bag Sampling		N
WAS		N	Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B139

Date: 17th November 2005

Instruments

1. CO pressure build in gas lines – not calibrating properly. Instrument switched off
2. TWC status lamp not switching off
3. CPC3025 ran out of butanol 30 min into flight
4. ARIES keyboard fault (work around solution)

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls None

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B139:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

4 x Upward Facing Cameras
4 x Downward Facing Cameras

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

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